

Recommended Reads – Focus on David Almond

The breadth of David Almond's work is in focus for this rendition of our recommended reads, for Almond, one of only three authors from the UK to have won the Hans Christian Andersen Award to date, is bold in his experimentation with radically innovative literature for young readers. The texts introduced here illustrate a range of formats: a picturebook, a play, and a young adult novel, starting off with one of Almond's extraordinary hybrid, richly illustrated texts, which will not conform to a recognized format.

Almond, David (2008)

The Savage

Illustrated by Dave McKean

Walker Books

Recommended by Michael C. Prusse

David Almond's novella *The Savage* could probably be best described as a 'hybrid' (Hateley, 2012, p. 176), to apply an attribute that Kimberley Reynolds had previously used when writing about Philipp Pullman's *Spring-heeled Jack* (Reynolds, 1994, p. 66). The hybrid nature of Almond's text refers to the fact that it consists of two media formats. There is a text-based tale presented as detached autobiography in the first person and a graphic narrative, illustrated by Dave McKean, that portrays the 'Savage' in the third person.

The protagonist of the verbal text, Blue Baker, is the author of the graphic passages, which he writes to overcome his traumatic experiences, the loss of his father due to a heart attack and the bullying by Hopper, a nasty, smoking, older kid. Blue, who lives with his Mam and his sister Jess in 'the little town of Saltwell' (Almond, 2008, p. 12), is sceptical when his school counsellor suggests that he write about his thoughts and feelings to deal with the unsettling events. Hateley (2012, p. 172) links this to the problems of a reluctant boy reader, however Blue is not described as being generally averse to reading but as someone who has clear preferences –

he hates 'all that stuff about wizards and fairies' but enjoys 'blood and guts and adventures' (Almond, 2008, p. 12).

Instead of recording his emotions and reflections, Blue invents the 'Savage', a character that lives independently in the wilderness and is not afraid of anything – on the contrary, he is a figure that inspires awe and fear in others. At this point, the narrative consists of prose passages in which the narrator mostly talks about his situation and in what manner he was inspired to create the story of the Savage. Hence, readers are given a metanarrative on authorship, on how to write a story, the ways a protagonist can evolve, and on the 'healing power of storytelling' (Bland, 2014a, p. 94). The Savage's graphic tale is combined with annotations that are brimming with spelling mistakes and thus allude to the writer's younger age when first designing his tale.

As the narrative proceeds, the two genres, traditional novel, and graphic novel, gradually begin to merge: 'Sometimes, it was nearly like I was him and he was me' (Almond, 2008, p. 31). When Blue runs away from school and enters the Savage's cave in the forest, he realizes that he has found his *doppelgänger*, his alter ego, his wild side. In a plot reversal of Stevenson's *Dr Jekyll and Mr Hyde*, the Savage becomes a part of his personality.

It is the two media formats combined with its shortness that make the text attractive for classroom usage. Before reading, students could be asked what associations they have with the noun 'savage' and then be given the task to draw or paint how they imagine such a character. The beginning of Chapter Two, in which Blue rhetorically asks what the use of swearing is if he is not permitted to do so in dire circumstances (Almond, 2008, p. 13), lends itself for a lesson on taboo words. In an ELT context, swearing is usually avoided, even though in extramural activities students are regularly exposed to it when they consume series, games, movies, music etc. While commonly familiar with the unspoken rules in their mother tongue, in English they move in uncharted territory and require a teacher's guidance on sociocultural appropriacy.

Blue's writing would probably not meet the expectations of most English teachers, but he is creative and poetic. A good example is the description of the bully Hopper: 'He walked around smoking and sneering and spitting and swearing' (Almond, 2008, p. 15). Another classroom task could consist of collecting adjectives or verbs with alliterative or onomatopoeic qualities and using them to portray people.

Young Blue's spelling is not perfect. More advanced learners could be asked to work in

pairs with (short) passages from the graphic narrative. They ought to look for misspelled words, and make suggestions, how they would correct them. In a teacher education environment, student teachers could explore the best ways to help students improve their writing skills: What would be an adequate method to turn Blue into a competent speller?

Finally, the hybrid nature of the text constitutes an ideal model of multimodalities and multiliteracies. Therefore, students might explore the difference between visual and verbal literacy, learn about narrative aspects such as mimesis and diegesis, and discuss the process of becoming a creator, an author, by means of Blue's example. How do the two narratives work?

Further suggestions for classroom activities can be found in Bland (2014b).

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Dr Michael C. Prusse is Professor of ELT at Zurich University of Teacher Education. His research focuses on language in professional contexts, pedagogical content knowledge, and teaching literature in the ELT classroom. Recent publications consider refugee narratives (2022), in *ETAS-Journal* 39(1), transmedia storytelling (2022), in *Foreign Language Learning in the Digital Age*, C. Lütge (Ed.), and using literature in the classroom (2023), in C. Amerstorfer & M. von Blanckenburg (Eds.), *Activating and Engaging Learners and Teachers: Perspectives for English Language Education*.